

Numerical Analysis of Viscoelastic Creep and Transverse Cracking in Fiber-reinforced Composites

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Finite element modeling of viscoelastic creep behavior and transverse cracking in fiber-reinforced composites

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Abstract

Fiber-reinforced composites are essential in the aerospace industry, highlighting the need for an in-depth understanding of their durability. This study introduces a novel approach that integrates viscoelasticity and damage evolution based on continuum damage mechanics, employing finite element analysis. The method utilizes an anisotropic viscoelastic constitutive law to examine creep behavior under constant stress, decomposing stresses into equilibrium and non-equilibrium components. Moreover, it integrates a transverse crack damage variable associated with crack density. After solving stiffness equations, a detailed analysis of transverse crack propagation is conducted. This technique was applied to creep tests on carbon fiber-reinforced plastics and 3D woven ceramic matrix composites, resulting in strain and crack density profiles. The numerical simulations successfully reproduced experimental outcomes. The developed method offers a comprehensive tool for analyzing transverse crack propagation under viscoelastic creep conditions through finite element analysis, significantly enhancing design considerations by incorporating aspects of long-term durability.

Background

CFRP fan blades

Turbine blades
crafted by CMCs

CFRP laminate[2].

Creep tests cause the transverse cracks in CMCs [3].

Applications of PMCs and CMCs in GE9X [1]

1. High bypassing (larger size)
 - **CFRP** fan blades/case
2. Improvement in combustion efficiency
 - **CMC** turbine blades

Time-dependent damage

[1] <https://www.geaviation.com/commercial/engines/ge9x-commercial-aircraft-engine>

[2] Asadi et al., *Compos. B Eng.*, 2011.

[3] Ikarashi Y. et al., *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 2020.

Objective

Previous studies : theoretical model

Transverse cracking under creep tests [1].

- ✓ Transverse cracking density enables quantitative evaluation of damage [1,2,3]
- The long-term durability of components can be evaluated by finite element method (FEM).

[1] Berton T. et al., *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*, 2016.

[2] Ogi and Takao, *Advanced Composite Materials*, 2001.

[3] Ikarashi Y. et al., *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 2020.

FEM modeling of creep deformation and transverse cracking

Efforts in this presentation

(1) Anisotropic viscoelastic constitutive law

- Different viscoelasticity in fiber direction/transverse.

(2) Transverse crack damage model

- Crack density - Damage variable relationship.
- Time-dependent damage propagation.

(3) Validation

- Transverse crack propagation during creep testing behavior during creep tests.

Generalized Maxwell model

Transverse crack damage model

An isotropic viscoelasticity

Generalized Maxwell model

➤ Linear spring + damper

✓ Voigt notation:

$$\sigma_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^6 C_{ij}(t) \varepsilon_j(0) + \sum_{j=1}^6 \int_0^t C_{ij}(t - \tau) \frac{\partial \varepsilon_j(\tau)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \quad (1)$$

$$C_{ij}(t) = C_{ij}^0 - \sum_{k=1}^N C_{ij}^k \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\alpha_T T_k}}\right) \quad (2)$$

Generalized Maxwell model

Discretization

$$\sigma_i(t) = \sum_{j=1}^6 C_{ij}^0(t) \varepsilon_j(0) - \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^6 q_{ij}^k \quad (3)$$

Static component

Non-equilibrium component

C_{ij}^0 : initial stiffness
 C_{ij}^k : relaxation stiffness

$$q_{ij}^k(t_{n+1}) = e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_T T_k}} q_{ij}^k(t_n) + C_{ij}^k \varepsilon(t_{n+\theta}) \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta t}{\alpha_T T_k}}\right) \quad (4)$$

Transverse cracking (1)

Crack density-damage variable [1]:

Crack density ρ :

➤ Number of cracks/length of observed area

Damage model [1]:

➤ Damage variables d_{ii} associated with ρ

$$d_{ii} = \frac{2\rho}{\beta_{ii}} \tanh \frac{\beta_{ii}}{2\rho}$$

Continuous damage model [2]:

➤ Applied to elastic compliance S^0 [2], relaxation elasticity C^k

$$S_{ii}^0 = (1 - d_{ii})^{-1} S_{ii,ini}^0$$

$$C_{ii}^k = (1 - d_{ii}) C_{ii,ini}^k$$

β_{ii} : Material constants
 S_{ii}^0 : Elastic compliance

Representative volume
elements RVEs [1]

[1] S. Onodera et al., *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*, 2022.

[2] C. Lopes, P. Camanho, Z. Gürdal, et al., *Compos Sci Technol*, 2009.

Transverse cracking (2)

Transverse crack propagation :

- Energy-stress criteria with time development [1]

Energy criterion

$$G(\rho) \geq G_C$$

G : Energy release rate
 G_C : Fracture toughness

- The energy release rate assumes that cracks occur at equal intervals.

$$G(\rho) = \frac{U\left(\frac{\rho}{2}\right) - 2U(\rho)}{A_{tr}}$$

U : Strain energy
 A_{tr} : Cross-sectional area

Time dependence of the fracture toughness [2]

$$G_C(t') = \frac{G_C^0}{2} \left(1 + \exp\left(-\frac{t'}{10^4}\right) \right)^{0.807}$$

G_C^0 : Initial value

t' : Accumulated time after creep initiation

[1] S. Onodera et al., *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*, 2022.

[2] T. Berton et al., *Compos Struct.* 2018.

Transverse cracking (3)

Transverse crack propagation :

- Energy-stress criteria with time development [1]

Stress-criterion

- Judging damage onset

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}(\rho)}{\sigma_{22C}}\right)^2 + \left(\alpha \frac{\sigma_{44}(\rho)}{\sigma_{22C}}\right)^2 + \left(\beta \frac{\sigma_{55}(\rho)}{\sigma_{22C}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (12)$$

$$\text{※} \alpha = \beta = 1$$

Intralaminar strength time dependence

- Intralaminar strength loss during creep testing

$$\sigma_{22C}(t') = k_d \sigma_{22C}^0 + (1 - k_d) \left(\exp\left(-\frac{t'}{T_d}\right) \right)^m \quad (13)$$

When both energy and stress criteria are satisfied
➤ Crack propagation

σ_{22C} : Intralaminar strength
 k_d
 m
 T_d } Fitting parameters

[1] S. Onodera et al., *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*, 2022.

[2] T. Berton et al., *Compos Struct.* 2018.

Transverse cracking (4): Flowchart

Numerical procedure :

Transverse cracking :

➤ Evaluate the crack density of each element.

Viscoelasticity: **implicit**

Transverse cracking:
explicit.

Validation analysis: CFRP(T800H/#3631)

- ✓ CFRP-Cross-ply laminate ($[0/90_3]_s$)
- ✓ Viscoelasticity : Applied in the transverse direction to the fiber
- ✓ Applied stress: 510 MPa, 530 MPa
- ✓ **Strain-history** : Element average of model center.
- ✓ **Transverse crack density** : Average value of 90° layer elements

[1] Ogi and Takao, *Advanced Composite Materials*, 2001.

Validation analysis: CFRP(T800H/#3631)

- ✓ Determine stress criterion parameters k_d, T_d , and m using crack density history [1].
 - **Good reproduction of strain history of test results**
- ✓ Only viscoelasticity model deviates from experimental results
 - **Contribution of time-dependent damage is significant.**

[1] Ogi and Takao, *Advanced Composite Materials*, 2001.

Validation analysis: CMC

- ✓ Orthogonal woven fabric of CMC [1]
- ✓ Mosaic model consisting of X, Y fiber bundles, pure matrix [1]
- ✓ Viscoelasticity: Applied in fiber direction

- ✓ **Strain history**: Calculated from unit cell model load direction displacement
- ✓ **Crack density**: Elements average of Y fiber bundle

Validation analysis: CMC

- ✓ Consistent with the crack estimation curve in previous study [1] (w/o time dependency damage, $k_d=1$)
- Damage to fiber bundle Y is accelerated by relaxation of fiber bundle X.
- ✓ Load strain history at 100 MPa deviates from experiment
- Consistent with experimental results when assuming no damage

Validation analysis: CMC

➤ Strain/damage distribution plotted at 120 MPa, creep test 40003 (s) elapsed

- ✓ Stronger strain and damage distribution occurs in fiber bundle Y surrounded by fiber bundle X.
- Damage to fiber bundle Y increases due to stress relaxation caused by the viscoelasticity of fiber bundle X.
- **Creep damage mechanism of fabric CMC at the microscale is reproduced.**

Development of a Quantitative Evaluation Method for Transverse Cracks in Fiber-Reinforced Composites Using FEM

- Anisotropic viscoelastic constitutive laws and a time-dependent transverse crack propagation model were implemented into the FEM.
 - The method was validated through creep tests of CFRP and CMC, showing good agreement in both crack density and creep deformation.
 - This study enables damage evaluation of 90° plies under creep loading using crack density.
- Combined with fiber-direction damage and delamination models, it supports long-term durability assessment.

